

TABLE 1—VARIATION OF TOTAL ESSENTIAL OIL AND ITS MAJOR CONSTITUENTS FROM THE LEAVES

Constituent Mol%	July	August	September	October	November	December	January	February	March	April	May
Eugenol	69.89	40.78	46.14	64.19	63.49	57.79	53.68	49.56	56.65	50.19	46.18
Methyleugenol	24.81	12.08	14.34	16.92	5.19	3.41	6.54	9.95	8.53	7.17	11.35
Caryophyllene	2.96	32.15	24.19	10.55	13.68	18.56	22.32	26.08	22.29	22.61	23.10
Others	2.34	14.99	15.33	8.34	17.64	20.24	17.46	14.41	12.53	20.03	19.37
Total essential oil (g/100 g of fresh leaves)	0.35	0.38	0.52	0.79	0.86	0.97	0.58	0.60	0.65	0.74	0.68

Experimental

Isolation of essential oil from the leaves: Plants were grown in the middle of June and fresh leaves (100 g) were collected on the 15th day of every month from July to May and hydrodistilled in a Cleavanger apparatus for 90 min. The essential oil was collected over ether. After evaporation of ether, the oil was dried over anhydrous $MgSO_4$, weighed and stored at 0°.

Glc analysis of the oil: The essential oil in each case was analysed directly by a programmed column temperature glc run (isothermal at 110° for 3 min, 3°/min upto 140°, 25 min isothermally at 140°) on a 10% SE-30 on Chromosorb WHP glass column (2 m × 1/8" i.d.) with flame ionisation detector. The major constituents of the oil were characterised by co-chromatography with the authentic samples of essential oils (Dragoco, West Germany). A Becker (Pakard 419) gas chromatograph was used. The response factor of the components was determined using the standards.

Results and Discussion

It was observed that the essential oil content of leaves (Table 1) gradually increased from the month July (oil content was minimum) to a maximum in December and then decreased in January and again increased upto the month April and fell in May. Hence, essential oil may be commercially isolated from the leaves of *O. sanctum* mainly in the months from October to January under local condition. It is better not to isolate the essential oil from the immature plants from July to September due to the low content of essential oil in scanty leaves during this period. It is also difficult to isolate large amount of essential oil from February to May due to insufficient growth of fresh leaves.

Glc analyses of the essential oils revealed the presence of at least thirteen components in each case, among which only eugenol, methyleugenol and caryophyllene are the major constituents throughout the observation period (almost total life period of the plant) and the amount of remaining constituents (designated as 'Others' in Table 1) is low.

The maximum availability of eugenol and methyleugenol in total essential oil was observed in

July whereas that of caryophyllene was recorded in August. For commercial purpose, however, eugenol, methyleugenol and caryophyllene may be isolated from the essential oil of the leaves of *O. sanctum* collected during October – December, October, and November – January, respectively.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. M. A. Choudhuri, Head, Department of Botany, Burdwan University for his kind help.

References

1. E. GUENTHER, "The Essential Oils", R. E. Krieger Pub. Co., Huntington, 1975, Vol. II, pp. 105, 517, 520.
2. B. M. LAWRENCE, J. W. HOGG, S. J. TERHUNE and N. PICHITAKUL, *Flavour Ind.*, 1972, 3, 47.
3. R. N. LAL, T. K. SEN and M. C. NIGAM, *Perfum. Kosmet.*, 1978, 59, 230.
4. S. N. SOBTI, P. PUSHPANGADAN, B. L. BRADU and B. B. JAIN, *Indian Perfumer*, 1979, 23, 16.
5. S. DUTT, *Indian Soap J.*, 1940, 6, 248.
6. S. K. PAREEK, M. L. MAHESHWARI and R. GUPTA, *Indian Perfumer*, 1980, 24, 93.
7. B. B. DEY and M. A. CHOUDHURI, *Indian perfumer*, 1980, 24, 199.

Evaluation of Olive Fruit (*Olea europaea*) Oil Recently Grown in Jammu and Kashmir State

S. K. KATIYAR* and A. K. BHATIA

Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu Tawi-180 001

Manuscript received 21 September 1987, accepted 3 February 1988

OLEA *europaea* is extensively cultivated in some mediterranean countries. Olive fruit oil is known to have some medicinal properties^{1,2}. India imports the oil from some European countries to fulfill its domestic requirements. Recently, some exotic varieties of olive from Italy and Spain have been introduced in some parts of Himachal Pradesh, Uttar Pradesh and Jammu and Kashmir States. Chemical investigations of two varieties, 'Ascotrinia' and 'Ascolina', grown in Jammu region have been carried out for appraising the suitability of their oils.

Experimental

Healthy, mature and ripe olive fruits were collected from its growing area at Bhadrawah in Jammu region at an altitude of about 1000 m above the mean sea level to study their physicochemical characteristics. The average weight, size, and mesocarp and kernel ratio of the fruits were observed. Moisture, ash, oil and protein content in the fruits were assayed by AOAC methods⁹. The oil was extracted from the mesocarp of the fruits by petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and purified⁴ for studying the fatty acid composition. The methyl esters of fatty acids were analysed through glc following the procedure of Kates⁵. A Pye–Unicam glc instrument equipped with hydrogen flame ionisation detector was used having glass column (200 cm × 0.6 cm) packed with 15% Reoplex on 80/100 mesh Chromosorb-W. Nitrogen was used as carrier gas with a flow rate of 35 ml min⁻¹. The column was operated isothermally at 190°; the injection port and detector temperatures being 270° and 300°, respectively.

Results and Discussion

The mesocarp of ripe olive fruits contained total ash, 2.1–2.4%; oil, 12.1–19.4%; crude protein, 2.5–2.8%; and moisture, 46.5–60.3%. On dry-weight basis, the oil constitutes 30–36% of the mesocarp. Fruits of 'Ascolina' are larger in size and weight (6.6 g/fruit) and having higher moisture content (60.3%) in comparison to 'Ascotrinia' having smaller size and lower weight (2.9 g/fruit) and moisture (46.5%) contents (Table 1). Iodine values of oil of both the varieties are lower than the values reported^{6–8}. The oil contained 0.9% unsaponifiable matter and 1.1–1.3% free fatty acids. These characteristics of lower iodine value and unsaponifiable

matter are within the acceptable limits of edibility^{9–10}.

Oleic acid constitutes 65.0 and 73.4% of the oil in Ascotrinia and Ascolina varieties, respectively (Table 1). In addition to oleic acid, palmitic and linoleic acids are the other constituents of the oil which constitute 24.5 and 16.0%, and 10.0 and 10.5% in Ascotrinia and Ascolina, respectively. A 0.5% eicosenoic acid was also found in Ascotrinia fruit oil (Table 1). The olives grown in Jammu region have marked similarity to those grown in Himachal Pradesh¹¹.

The characteristics of olive fruits and their oils obtained from Jammu region are similar to that of the European varieties. Moreover, the oil having lower iodine value and free fatty acids shows its greater dietary acceptance.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to Miss R. K. Jamwal, Chairman, Instrument Division for glc analysis.

References

1. A. K. NADKARNI, "Indian Materia Medica", Popular Book Depot., Bombay, 1927, p. 870.
2. G. CHRISTAKIS, M. K. FORDYCE and C. S. KUTRZ, "Proceedings 3rd International Congress on the Biological Value of Olive Oil", Greece, 1980, p. 85.
3. "Official Methods of Analysis", Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Washington, D.C., 1984.
4. J. FOLCH, M. LEES and G. H. SLOANE-STANLEY, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1957, **226**, 497.
5. M. KATES, *J. Lipid Res.*, 1964, **5**, 132.
6. D. PEARSON, "The Chemical Analysis of Foods", Chemical Publishing Co., New York, 1971, p. 508.
7. M. B. JACOB "Chemical Analysis of Foods and Food Products", Van Nostrand, New York, 1958, p. 365.
8. J. GRACIAN in "Analysis and Characterization of Oils, Fats and Fat Products", ed. H. A. BOEKENOGEN, Interscience, New York, 1968, p. 315.
9. A. G. WOODMAN, "Food Analysis", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1941, p. 170.
10. Annon, "The Prevention of Food Adulteration Act", Eastern Book Co., Lucknow, 1954, p. 119.
11. S. K. KATIYAR, Unpublished data.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS AND FATTY ACID COMPOSITION* OF OLIVE FRUIT OIL

Parameters	Ascotrinia	Ascolina
(a) Fruit		
Weight of fruit (g)	2.9	6.6
Kernel (%)	20	16
Pulp (%)	80	84
Moisture (%)	46.5	60.3
Ash (%)	2.1	2.4
Protein (%)	2.6	2.8
Oil (%)	19.4	12.1
Oil (dry wt. basis) (%)	36	30
(b) Fruit oil		
Iodine value	68	69
Saponification value	199	197
Unsaponifiable matter (%)	0.9	0.9
Free fatty acids (%)	1.1	1.3
Fatty acids :		
C16:0	24.5	16.0
C18:0	—	trace
C18:1	65.0	73.4
C18:2	10.0	10.5
C18:3	traces	—
C20:1	0.5	—

*Values are means of triplicate determinations.

AAS Determination of Zinc after Separation with Liquid Chelating Exchanger and its Application to the Ganga River Water

SHUVENDU S. BHATTACHARYYA

and

ARABINDA K. DAS*

Department of Chemistry, University of Burdwan,
Burdwan-713 104

Manuscript received 7 January 1987, revised 17 July 1987,
accepted 3 February 1988

FLAME and flameless atomic absorption spectrophotometric (AAS) determination of zinc has been described by several authors^{1–5}. In most of the cases, different chelating agents have been used